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ENGLISH AND HEBREW METAPHORS WITH EDIBLE PLANT NAMES

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Abstract

The aim of the work is to study English and Jewish figurative language with the names of edible plants and culinary motivation from an interlingual and intercultural perspective. For the first time, we offer a systematic lexicographic description of this layer of Food metaphors, including the identification, analysis, and classification. The result of the corpus of 119 metaphors systematization (75 English and 44 Hebrew, are English and Hebrew tables with names of edible plants, biblical and widespread, full, partial equivalents, and ethnocultural metaphors. In quantitative terms English metaphors predominate over Hebrew ones, the English list of plant names is more extensive, although there are exclusive plants both in the English and Hebrew list. This study focuses on conceptual metaphors, linguacultural comments, lexical and semantic characteristics, similarities, and differences in English and Hebrew figurative language.

Keywords: food metaphor, conceptual metaphor, edible plants, figurative language, English, Hebrew, cross-linguistic perspective.

1. Introduction Metaphors with Edible Plants1. Introduction

Food is a universal human need and Food metaphors (a poetically or rhetorically ambitious use of words, a figurative, as opposed to literal use, Metaphor) are very productive in modern discourses because they are "a mirror of a linguistic community's historical, social, political, and cultural story"(Pinnavaia, 2015: 455). The names of botanical crops as highly productive edible plants such as trees, shrubs, and herbs, are semantic models of figurative language (Pamies, et al, 2015). Due to the fact that individuals and societies denote their ethnic, national, social, class, gender, and linguistic identity through food figurative language(Metaphor, FOOD A) metaphors are very important for multicultural communication as a symbolic, interpretive, transactional, contextual process, in which people from different cultures create shared meanings. (Lustig & Koester, 2007:46). Metaphoric Competence is acquired in second language learning and teaching as a part of

grammatical, textual sociolinguistic competence (Littlemore& Low, 2006:268).

The theoretical base of this work is Lakoff's theory concern the conceptual metaphor as a universal process of human thinking reflected in language structures and leads to the interaction of two cognitive structures or areas: the source domain and the target domain with complicated links between them (Lakoff, 1980)- and the ideas on the metaphor cultural dependence and the multilingual approach (Dobrovolsky& Pirainen, 2005; Piirainen, 2012:62).

In recent decades, a large number of linguistic research focuses on phraseology or figurative language (a set of set expressions), and, in particular, Food concepts and metaphors in different languages. An important contribution to food metaphors studies contributed books and studies on food Metaphors in English(Pinnavaia, 2018), Portuguese (Monteiro, 2011), Spanish (Pamies, 2011, 2014); and Russian (Pomarolli, 2021).

Intensive developing contrastive studies of English and European and non-European languages include research, i.e. Portuguese, Spanish and Chinese (Monteiro et al., 2018); French, German, and Spanish (Pinnavaia, 2015); Romanian (Ionesco, 2017); Croatian (Majic, 2017); Spanish (Negro, 2019); Russian, Italian (Yurina, et al, 2017); numerous languages (Pamies, 2015); Russian, German (Babaeva et al., 2020).

Thereby, the English food concept is described and presented at different levels but not find the study of Hebrew food metaphors like research of English and Hebrew metaphors with an edible plant (furthermore - MEP), and this study, aims to fill this gap.

Materials and Methods

The study corpus is 116 metaphors (74 English and 42 Hebrew) with the names of edible plants namely fruits, nuts, vegetables, starch, bulbous plants, herbs, and spices that can be used as food, raw or processed, parts or all. Cereals, mushrooms, and oil plants do not appear in this list because they require special deep study. A figurative metaphors corpus comprises idioms, set expressions, phraseological units, and paremiological units as proverbs, maxims, and sayings collected from electronic explanatory and phraseological dictionaries, token search on the Internet, Hebrew newspapers (Yediot Ahronot) and radio programs (Reshet B). This large sample is a pilot version that does not claim to be complete.

Below is the applicated procedure: definition of figurative language, gathering of metaphors in the above sources; listing the edible plant names of each language, and comparing the equivalents. The Jewish Bible (Old Testament) has been defined as the main source of ancient equivalents, late equivalents were divided into full and partial without diachrony and source research, and ethnocultural metaphors were analyzed separately for each language. The systematics results were presented in five tables upbuild on the color idioms classification principles (Kigel, 2022), namely, object and human characteristics, and finally human activity. Then the national-cultural comments and formulated conceptual metaphors were added.

The study contributes to further linguistic research in comparative, and contrastive linguistics, psycholinguistics, lexicographic, and lexicological lexicology, lexicography, language theory, cognitive linguistics, and ethnolinguistics. The research materials can be used in textbooks, for the compilation of educational and educational dictionaries, paremiological and phraseological corpora of each language, and parallel corpora of two languages. In practice, the English and Hebrew lexicology data are applicable for intercultural communication, L2 classes, interpretation, human, and automatic translation.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 The names of edible plants

The list of English names includes fruits and nuts (apple, grape, fig, olive, lemon, banana, cherry, pear,

plum, oranges, melon); Berries (raspberries, strawberries); Vegetable (tomato, cucumber, cabbage); Legumes (lentils, beans, peas); Starch plants (potato, sweet potato, corn, turnip); Bulbous plants (onions, garlic); Spices and spices (carrots, peppers, parsnips, mustard). The list of names in Hebrew includes fruits (apple, grape, cherry, fig, lemon, banana, melon, olive etrog, pomegranate), vegetables (cabbage, tomato, reddish); Starch plants (potato, sweet potato); Bulbous plants (onions, garlic); Herbs and spices (carrots, peppers).

The unique plant names usually reflect the flora of the commune's country of residence. In the English list, among fruits exist berries, pear, plum, pineapple, orange, melon, strawberry, and raspberry appear, and among vegetables and other plants - beans, peas, celery, white root, parsley, cucumber, corn, turnip, parsnip and mustard, which are lacunar for Hebrew. Lacunar's names for English are etrog, pomegranate, and radish.

The English names represent native plants of English-speaking countries and former British colonies and consist of 31 names, while Hebrew names present plants cultivated in Israel with 21 names.

The following historical excursus tries to explain English metaphors' big quantitative prevalence in Hebrew ones.

English and Hebrew are geographically distant, genetically unrelated languages, and the developmental history of the two languages is very different. English is a West Germanic language of the Indo-European language family, and its earliest forms date back to the 5th century. As a result of consistent development, English has become the global lingua franca. It is estimated that about 1,750,000 people used English as their mother tongue, second language, or foreign language, it is the most important language in newspaper and book publishing, telecommunications, scientific publishing, international trade, mass entertainment, and diplomacy (Crystal, 1997). The modern status of the English language is a consequence of the colonial policy of the British Empire in the 19th and first half of the 20th century, as well as the global influence of the United States in the 20th and 21st centuries. Currently, English-speaking centers are located in England, America, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand (**English language**).

Hebrew, one of the oldest languages in the world, belongs to the Canaanite group of languages, and the earliest examples of a written Paleo-Hebrew language date back to the 10th century BC. After the destruction of the Second Temple in Jerusalem in 70 AD Jews scattered throughout the world. Having been the language of liturgy and literature for almost two millennia, but did not develop as a spoken language. As a result of the revival of Hebrew in the early 19th century, it became the spoken and written language, the main official language of the State of Israel. In 2013, about 9 million people in Israel, the United States, and other countries spoke Hebrew. countries (**Hebrew**). The English linguistic tradition also contributes to situations with more English metaphors than Hebrew ones.

Table 1.

Names of Edible Plants in English and Hebrew Metaphors

English	Hebrew
Fruit and Nuts apple, grape, fig, olive, lemon, banana, cherry, <i>pear, plum, oranges, melon</i>	תפוח, ענבים, תאנה, זית, לימון, בננה, דובדבן, תמר, שקד, אחרוג, רימון Apple, grapes, fig, olive, lemon, banana, cherry, date, almond, etrog, pomegranate
Berries <i>raspberry, strawberry</i>	-
Vegetable tomato, cabbage, <i>cucumber</i> Legumes lentils, <i>beans, peas</i>	עדשים, כרוב, עגבניה, צנון cabbage, tomato, lentils, reddish
Starch plants potatoes, sweet potatoes, <i>corn, turnip</i>	תפוחי אדמה, בטטה potatoes, sweet potatoes
bulbous plants onion, garlic, <i>leek</i>	בצל, שום onion, garlic
Herbs and spices carrots, <i>pepper, parsnip, mustard</i>	גזר, פלפל carrot, pepper

* italicized names are unique to this list

3.3 Biblical Metaphor Equivalents

The cultural and moral contribution of the Hebrew Bible (other names - Tanakh, Old Testament) to society and culture is generally recognized (Wiederkehr-Pollack, 2019) and, it is a source of borrowings in many languages including English (Van Hecke, 2020). Biblical Metaphors need lingua-cultural comments to explain the source and their use in modern discourse.

In the Bible story on Eden God commanded Adam and Eve to eat from every tree in the garden, but not from the "tree of the knowledge of good and evil". However, Eve, seduced by the serpent, ate the forbidden fruit and shared it with Adam. Having fallen into sin, the first men came aware of their "nudity" and make clothes from fig leaves. The metaphor *tree of the knowledge of good and evil and forbidden fruit* did not point out specific botanical kinds as the idiom fig leaf. Our analysis is consistent with the explanation that the generic name as a tree, fruit, flower, etc. are more conducive to conceptual metaphor, and potentially, more universal and the image of an apple in Bible illustrations appeared in the painters' imagination (Pamies, 2014, 100).

The metaphors *forbidden fruit, olive branch, and lentil stew* have modern extensions of the meaning that are evidenced that in the Jewish Bible described typical, universal, and time-lasting characters and situations. So, nowadays *forbidden fruit* is an illegal or immoral pleasure; *fig leaf* - covering a derogatory thing; *lentil stew (pottage)* is short-sighted wrong decisions because of an acute material need, an *olive branch* is a symbol of peace, and harmony and is drawn on the Emblem of Israel. These examples are evidence of semantic secularization when the metaphors lost their religious meaning and got updated meaning (Yadin &

Zuckermann, 2010:84) wherein Biblical expressions in Hebrew are a part of both religious and colloquial discourse.

The hypothesis that in English Biblical expressions are most often used in religious discourse while in Hebrew they are a part of both religious and colloquial discourse needs to be studied.

A number of English and Hebrew MEPs are widespread idioms with the source from Greek and French (myth, of Aesop and LaFontaine fabulous) e.g. the apple of discord, sour grapes, pull someone's chestnuts out of the fire) that prove the involvement of two languages in the world process of mutual language borrowing.

All the Biblical and Widespread Equivalent MEPs can be analyzed as conceptual metaphors according to the source domain and the target domain and it is evidence of their generalizing ability potential.

Conceptual Metaphors(the source domain vs target domain)

Tree with fruits > knowledge *The tree of knowledge of good and evil*

Fruit > results as A. Pamies figured out (Pamies et al., 2015) *He ate the fruit of his deeds*

Fruit > reproduction *the fruit of the belly*

Fruit > physical good vs spiritual ones *pottage, pull someone's chestnuts out of the fire*

Fruit > peace and agreement *olive branch*

Fruit > trouble, an uncomfortable situation difficult issue *forbidden fruit, sour fruits, an apple of discord*

All Biblical Metaphors, to our dismay, refer to fruits and not to vegetables or other kinds of plants, except lentils.

Table 2.

English and Hebrew Biblical and Widespread Equivalents with Edible Plant Names	
Biblical Metaphor	Meaning
עץ הדעת טוב ורע בראשית בי The tree of knowledge of good and evil	The tree of the knowledge of good and evil God forbade mankind to eat fruit from this tree in Eden
פרי אסור בראשית ג' Forbidden fruit	A fruit not to be eaten to the command of God The modern extension - illegal or immoral indulgence, pleasure
פרי הבטן בראשית ל, פסוק ב the fruit of the belly	Embryo, woman's fertility
עלה תאנה בראשית ג, פסוק ז Fig leaf	The first people who had sinned realized theirs I was naked and covered myself with a fig leaf at the sight of God The modern extension - covering a derogatory thing
יונה עם עלה של זית בראשית פרק ח פסוק יא An olive branch	an offer or gesture of conciliation or goodwill The modern extension - a proposal of peace and agreement
אכל פרי מעליו ישעיהו ג', י' He ate the fruit of his deeds	A person bears the consequences of his actions The modern extension – the cause and consequence
תבשיל עדשים פרשת תולדות, פרק כ"ה, ספר בראשית For lentil stew	to sell, give up something for a petty temptation, at the cost of an insignificant profit The modern extension - short-sighted wrong decisions because of an acute material need
Nonbiblical Widespread Equivalents	
תפוח מחלוקת Greek Mythology Apple of discord	the core, or crux of an argument, or a small matter that could lead to a bigger dispute
פרי חמוץ Aesop's fable The Fox and the Grapes Sour fruits	an ungracious reaction after a loss or failure.
להוציא את הערמונים מהאש J. de la Fontaine Pull someone's chestnuts out of the fire	to do another person's difficult or dangerous work

3.2. English and Hebrew Equivalent Metaphors with Edible Plant names

English and Hebrew full equivalents with the same meaning and lexical-semantic structure in the source and target language e.g. hot potato, the apple never falls far from the tree, hard nut - are a few. However partial equivalents featured the similarity of content accompanied by variability in form (syntactic, semantic, or pragmatic aspects, inconsistencies between textual norms and linguistic forms) are widely represented. In these two languages and many of them are internationalism which means they are widespread in many languages and not only in English and Hebrew (Pirainen, 2012). The equivalents in different languages arose due to the similarity of the psychophysical experience of people living on Earth.

In recent decades, the main source language of borrowing is English as the leading language of cultural, social, technological, business, trade, education, and tourism in other areas (Crystal, 1997). A diachronic study of the mutual influence of English and Hebrew can be the task of a separate interesting work.

The most productive change in partial equivalents is the change of plant name: e.g. English-Hebrew pairs: the *cake* changed to *whipped cream* in the metaphor (*cherry on the cake/cherry on the cake with whipped cream*), turnip to cabbage or sweet potato; bean, potato, nut to garlic shell (not worth a *nutshell/garlic glove*).

In the full equivalent *When life gives you lemons, make lemonade* Hebrew and English meaning is similar but lemon in English is a symbol of everything bad, and in Hebrew lemon (*lemon adds a lot*) also has a positive connotation as a local fruit, which in the early 19th century was one of Israel's most exported goods.

The partial MEPs meaning have a few differences e.g. English expression *squeezed lemon/orange* is associated with extracting benefit from an object or situation, and in Hebrew, it is clearly associated with a human factor - namely, with a lack of human energy and, in addition, in Hebrew, there is no as synonym as orange.

As a consequence, the English idiom *spice of life* used the generalized name *spice* while in the Hebrew parallel is mentioned as a lemon. However, the partial equivalents of *Banana Republic/רפובליקת בננות/Republicat Banannot* create a rhyme because the Hebrew word for banana is plural.

Our analysis concurs with the conclusion that the source of one metaphorical model can use both fruits and vegetables, fruit can be a source domain and also the target domain (Pamies, 2014), and the same plant can have both positive and negative connotations and, in general, fruits feature more positive connotations and vegetables more negative ones (Pinavaia, 2018).

Table 3.

English and Hebrew Equivalent Metaphors with Edible Plant Names	
Full Equivalents	
Metaphor and Meaning	Hebrew
Banana Republic corruptive country	רפובליקת בננות
When life gives you lemons, make lemonade turning negative events into something positive, making the most of negative situations	כשהחיים נותנים לך לימונים, תכין לימונד
fruitful a tree, plant, or land, producing much fruit, products; fertile	פורה פרי עטו <i>The modern extension – the work result</i>
hot potato a controversial or difficult issue	תפוח אדמה לוהט
the apple never falls far from the tree (Offspring grow up to be like their parents in behavior or physical characteristics)	התפוח לעולם לא נופל רחוק מהעץ
hard, tough nut to crack difficult to understand or persuade tough nut to crack (a challenging problem)	אגוז קשה
Pepper energy, vitality Peppery: Hot-tempered	פלפל מפולפל
If life gives you a lemon, make lemonade (make the best of a difficult situation)	<i>If life gives you a lemon, make lemonade</i>
Partial Equivalents	
The cherry on the cake (the best and most enjoyable part)	הדובדבן שבקצפת <i>cherry on whipped cream</i>
the spice of life (makes life interesting, exciting, enjoyable)	לימון מוסיף המון <i>Lemon adds a lot</i> <i>A small addition greatly improves the thing or situation, advertising slogan</i>
in a nutshell (brief)	כקליפת השום
Fruitable producing good results; beneficial; profitable	פורה
not worth a hill of beans (worthless) small potatoes (insignificant)	שווה לקליפת שום <i>Not worth a garlic clove</i>
A stick and a carrot reward and punishment	מקל וגזר
squeezed lemon/ orange To make use of everything someone or something has to offer)	לימון סחוט <i>Lack of energy after reaching, exhausted from hard work</i>
A rotten apple, bad apple, one bad (or rotten) apple spoils the whole bunch, barrel a bad reputation, a negative person	תפוח אחד רקוב בערימה
No more brains than a turnip (foolish)	ראש, בטטה ראש כרוב

Ethnocultural Metaphors Ethnocultural Metaphors contain unique national and cultural information, and their semantics express unique environment, material, and spiritual cultures as customs, religion, philosophies, and other factors. The national differences are reflected in the English MEPs with beans, mustard, parsnip, and Hebrew MEPs as citron, and almond.

English Ethnocultural MEPs presented in this study belong to the group of Human external and internal personal characteristics, Human activity, and a big capacity Miscellaneous group will be the object of the special study.

Conceptual Metaphors(the source domain vs target domain)

Fruit > appearance - *as red as a cherry; a carrot top.*

Fruit > cognitive practice - *apples and oranges(comparison); from soup to nuts(order).*

Fruit > excellent - *bad an apple of the eye; the cherry on the cake; apple pie, a peach, real plum vs lemon.*

Fruit > effort and its results - *fruits of labor; to bear Fruit; cut the mustard; he that would eat the kernel must crack the nut.* This theme already presented deathly and with many examples in numerous languages(Pamies et al., 2015).

Fruit > an opportunity - *bite at the cherry; have a second bite of the cherry.*

Fruit > unexpected - *to upset the apple cart; how do you like them apples.*

Fruit > unreasonable behavior - *go bananas; nutty as a fruitcake.*

Fruit, Vegetable > negative characteristics - *rotten to the core; not the clean potato; worm in the apple.*

Vegetable > energy or lack of it - *full of beans; look as parsnips, veg out.*

The MEPs lexical-semantic characteristics

MEPs of *external similarity* (*peach fuzz*), and process similarity (*peel the onion*, low-hanging fruit) have an opaque motivation and MEP *go bananas*, *to drive bananas* have unclear motivation.

We found MEPs featured the antonymy (*cherry-lemon*; *squeezed lemon/ orange*), synonymy (*squeeze the lemon/orange*), variations (*not care/give/worth an onion a fig*).

In terms of parts of speech, except the derivation nutty (adjective) all plant name are nouns and in terms of stylistics, most MEPs present the literal lingual layer(The tree of knowledge of good and evil), neutral

style(apples and oranges), colloquial discourse (full of beans) and slang(go nuts).

Scholars noted that fruits have more positive connotations when vegetable has more negative ones (**Pin-navaia, 2015**) and our corpus supports this thesis(apple pie, real plum vs hot potato, veg out). The added note is that the same plant can have both positive and negative connotations (an apple in my eye vs a bad apple; be nuts about vs go nuts) and in the same metaphorical model use the name both fruits and vegetables e.g. negative characteristics (worm in the apple, not a clean potato potato); appearance(smooth and pale skin with light pink cheeks, a carrot top).

Table 4.

English Ethnocultural Metaphors

Human characteristics
Appearance as red as a cherry (ruddy, blood with milk) peaches and cream (smooth and pale skin with light pink cheeks) peach fuzz (small amount of hair growth) a carrot top (a red-haired) smart as a new-scraped carrot(overdress) like two peas in a pod(almost identical in appearance)
Energy-Lack of Energy full of beans (full of energy and life) look as parsnips(sour and bad-tempered) veg out (to spend time idly or passively) to become a vegetable(physically disabled)
Negative characteristics rotten to the core (thoroughly bad, worthless) not (quite) the clean potato (suspicious personality) worm in the apple)(something very bad in the best)
Human activity Cognitive practice Comparing apples and oranges (to uselessly compare unlike things) Apples for apples(comparison between related and similar things) Method From soup to nuts (from the beginning to the end) cut the mustard (come up to scratch, expectations, required standard; succeed)
Excellent -bad an apple in the eye (favorite, loved) cherry condition(excellent condition) the cherry on the cake(the best part) apple pie (neat and tidy) cherry-pick (to select the best) life is a bowl of cherries (life is as easy and pleasant) be nuts about (enjoy very much()) a peach(beautiful, excellent) real plum(a good opportunity) lemon (unsatisfactory)
Effort He that would eat the kernel must crack the nut (to achieve your desire you must make the necessary effort) One that would have the fruit must climb the tree(to enjoy something, you should make first the effort) Get blood out of a turnip(achieve the impossible, especially money) Result of effort Fruits of labor To Bear Fruit (positive results of efforts) a tree is known by its fruit(characteristics determined on the results) Low-hanging fruit (easily achieved)
an opportunity a bite at the cherry)- an opportunity to achieve something) have a second bite of the cherry (a second chance or a second opportunity)
Unexpected To upset the apple cart(to ruin plans, upset people) How do you like them apples (the USA, surprise e or shock) Go pear-shaped (gone wrong, an and unwanted result)

<p>Unreasonable behavior go bananas (excited, crazed), to drive bananas (to annoy or irritate) nutty as a fruitcake(irrational or crazy) go nuts(excited over)</p>
<p>Flatter an apple polisher)a flatterer) To polish an apple) to) To feed on soft corn(be extremely polite with someone)</p>
<p>Secret spill the beans (to reveal a secret) Even the corn has ears and potatoes have eyes (Never tell your family secrets)</p>

Hebrew Ethnocultural Metaphors Jewish nation and language exist more than five a thousand years, enjoy the globalization era fruits and keep their national and cultural identity through language evidence of flora (citron, pomegranate), keeping traditions (*creator of the fruit of the vine*, the blessing on the wine every Friday night, and semantic secularization in modern meaning extensions (*full as a pomegranate*).

When Ethnocultural Hebrew Bible metaphors came from high discourse (*a righteous person like a date palm will blossom*), there are MEPs in colloquial discourse(*apple in honey*) and many metaphors connected to slang (*nonsense in tomato juice*).

Some ethnocultural Hebrew metaphors are distinguishing with humor as a multi-century Hebrew linguistics tradition. Metaphor *like citrons after Sukkot* /like citrons after Sukkot, emphasize the dichotomy of urgent need vs complete worthless depending on time. Nonformal greeting to girls/בנות *bananas* emphasize the similarity of fruits and the beauty and cute young girls features).

Metaphors conclude the name of different plants, covering many themes, have both positive(as almond - diligent) and negative connotations(nonsense in tomato juice).

Borrowing from Yiddish (like citrons after Sukkot) and Arabic (once honey, once onion) demonstrate

effective methods for enriching a living and developing language. Although a number of Hebrew MEPs is not big, they add a very originality point of linguistic picture of the world.

Conceptual Metaphors (the source domain vs target domain)

Fruits > abundance, wealth, peace - *a man under our vine branch and under his fig tree; apple in honey;*

Fruits > the best part - *inside he ate his shell and threw it away*

Fruits > many talents and broad knowledge, hard-working - *full as a pomegranate; as almond*

Fruits > the material compensation for mental hardship - *nuts and raisins*

Vegetable >boring person - *dry as reddish*

Vegetable > disappointment - once a honey, once onion

(target domain vs the source domain)

A righteous person>a nice tree with plenty of fruits - a righteous person like a date palm will blossom

It found

English and Hebrew metaphorical models are a correspondence was in associating fruits with well-being, the best qualities of a person, object or situation, as well as with the productivity and results of persons labor.

Table 5.

Hebrew Ethnocultural Metaphors 8	
Ethnocultural Hebrew Bible metaphors	
מלא מצוות כרימון, מלא תורה כרימון ברכות נו full as a pomegranate Full of Torah, Torah scholar	Blessing during the Rosh Hashanah meal, promises to do many good deeds Modern extension – a person with many knowledge and new ideas
איש תחת גפנו ותחת תאנתו ד – פסוקים ג, מיכה ד A man under our vine branch and under his fig tree	A life of peace and quiet, and personal and financial security
אבות אכלו בוסר ושיני הילדים הושחזו ירמיהו, פרק ל"א, פסוק כ"ח Fathers ate unripened and the children's teeth were sharpened	Sons bear the punishment for the fathers' iniquities
תוכו אכל קליפתו זרק תלמוד בבלי, מסכת חגיגה – דף טו, עמוד ב Inside he ate his shell and threw it away	Choose only the best out of everything
בורא פרי הגפן משנה א, 'פרק ו, מסכת ברכות Creator of the fruit of the vine	The blessing on wine is one of the most important blessings
תפוח בדבש מנהג Apple in honey	A customary on the Rosh Hashanah eve to dip an apple in honey and say: ומתוקה כדבש ומתוקה: /may we have a good and sweet New Year
צדיק כתמר יפרח תהילים צב, יג A righteous person like a date palm will blossom	A good person will succeed in his ways
Ethnocultural Non Bible Hebrew metaphors	
איש אשכולות Eschalots' man	A man of many talents and very broad knowledge
שקדן As almond	hardworking
אגוזים וצימוקים Gift for children beginning to learn Torah טובים ומתוקים וצמקים ושקדים, אך דברי תורה מהם מתוקים	Nuts and raisins Raisins and almonds are good and sweet, but the words of the Torah are sweeter than them
יבש כמו צנון Dry as reddish	Boring person
שיטת הבצל The onion method	The method of dressing in layers
(בנות)בנות Girls, bananas	girls, nonformal greeting, humor
שטויות במיץ עגבניות Nonsense in tomato juice	Absolute nonsense, slang
כמו אתרוגים אחרי הסוכות Like citrons after Sukkot	The very important thing in past but now no longer effective; totally worthless, from Yiddish
פעם עסל פעם בסל Once a honey, once onion	A day - a success, a day - disappointment, slang, from Arabic

4. Conclusion

The two languages' full equivalents are connected to the English borrowing from the Jewish Bible and mutual borrowing from widespread sources.

Hebrew retains a strong connection with Bible Metaphors and the Humor as ancient Hebrew tradition using various methods of modernization and adaptation.

English and Hebrew metaphorical models are strong correspondence in associating fruits with well-being, the best qualities, as well as with the productivity and results of person's labor.

Among the later equivalents, there are an equal amount of full and partial ones with the change of phytonym as the most common method.

Ethnocultural Metaphors demonstrate big difference and very strong national identity.

Most figurative language units refer to fruits and, to lesser to vegetables and other plants.

In the future, it seems necessary to the generalization of Food Metaphors in two languages to investigate the drink, culinary metaphors, and diachronic side.

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